

Greener Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research

ISSN: 2276-7835 Impact Factor 2012 (UJRI): 0.7563 ICV 2012: 5.62

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present work is the realization of an electronic micro processor controlled by a PIC16F877 to control the power of an Ultrasound Generator. This is a module meant to ease the reading and the reproducibility of the power of an ultrasonic generator with brand name, Vibracell Sonics & Materials that we used for homogenization of liquid foods. Operating parameters such as power and time supplied by the Ultrasound Generator to the suspensions of variable nature must be solved by suitable action on the process considered, Ultrasound Generator. The control of these parameters should be based on the desired quality of the liquid to be homogenised.

Given the complex nature of the approach in controlling these parameters, their interpretation and reutilisation, this card was associated with a database manager named WINDEV14 MICROSOFT. The analysis method used is UP7.

This work is a part of an application that we developed and named "Logiciel de Pilotage du Générateur d'Ultrasons" (LoPiGULson; with english acronym: Control Software of Ultrasonic Generators). It is an application that allows not only to better coordinate research and monitoring of generator parameters but also the physical properties of liquid foods.

The power digital control card established, highly sensitive and linear, is conditioned to obtain answers in a band width of 1 Watt and perform measurements on a range of 0 to 250 Watts. Its realization as a facilitator of dependency does not change the basic function of the ultrasound generator.

Keywords: Control, Ultrasonic Signal, PIC16F877, Feed back control system, Liquid Food.

INTRODUCTION

In a world increasingly concerned about its food supply, equipment within the production mechanisms are in constant evolution. In order to reduce the particle size for homogenizing suspensions (Cucheval and Chow, 2008; Petit, 2002) in the production of juices of guavas, we used an ultrasonic generator of brand name Vibracell Sonics & Materials.

This ultrasound generator can operate up to a maximum frequency of 20 kHz and high-power (250 W). With power and duration both manually adjustable, we had initially qualified it as a visual dependence system. Nevertheless, the manual adjustment of ultrasound parameters is not accurate and presents the problem of reproducibility and repeatability. It has therefore proved useful to develop an electronic card for control of analog ultrasonic signals by digitizing, storing and displaying. The visual aspect allows us to judge a first approximation of the quality and quantity of power produced, and thus the size of the suspensions. As for storage, it allows us to generate a database for reproducibility and repeatability of the process.

Despite the significant improvements known by analog instruments each year, it is subject to inherent limitations that restrict its use on an increasing number of applications, hence its progressive replacement by digitalisation.

Digital has some advantages, relating to the quality of the measurement and treatment options results namely, the elimination of errors due to the operator and the remote control (Nieto and Paul, 1975). In our case, the integration of digital power allows us to pass in programmable logic (Tocci, 1992; Mayeux, 2005), built around the PIC16F877. The choice of this microcontroller is based on the adaptability of its internal architecture to developed system. As those of its generation, it has a high reliability and flexibility (Brian and Ritchie, 1978; Benoit, 2003).

It is important to mention that, to achieve the final realization of this application, the use of information systems module like an application package to integrate data and processes is necessary.

Therefore it is essential to adopt a method to simplify and better understand reality. Among the several modeling methods such as OMT, RACINE, MERISE, UP7, OOSE, APTE ... our choice was focused on the UP7

method, which is iterative and incremental. Moreover, it is based on UML as modelling language. As a tool for planning and management of our database, we opted for the WINDEV 14 MICROSOFT environment. In these statements, this article details the intelligent part of the device, as in the *Materials and Methods*. We shall then discuss *results and interpretation* section, and end with the *conclusion*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

In this work, the implementation of our application requires resources, both hardware and software. For this, we used a mass of titanium oxide $m = 1.5$ g in 200 ml of distilled water for the calibration of the ultrasound generator power. The microprocessor PIC16F877 is used for processing digital data which are transferred to memory. The computer DELL N5040 built for storage and large scale processing, has the appropriate characteristics including an Intel(R) Core (TM) i3CPUM380@2,53 GHz, a RAM of 4.00GB.

As support software we opted for the WINDEV 14 MICROSOFT environment, both useful for programming and database management.

Confirmation of the statements made based on power voltage during our manipulation was done through software ISIS of PROTEUS V.7.6, MICKRO C V.7003 trial version and IC-PROG V.1.05C.

For the preparation of guava juice to be homogenized, the conditions were defined by Ndjiya et al. (2012). The Ultrasound Generator is shown in Figure 1, while its main lines of operation are set out in the flowchart of Figure 2.

Figure 1: Ultrasound Generator « Vibracell Sonics & Materials

Figure 2: Flowchart of operation of an ultrasound generator

Ultrasound generator converts the mains voltage (220 V, 50 Hz) into a high frequency electric power (250 W, 20 kHz). This high electric frequency is transmitted to a piezoelectric transducer which converts it into mechanical energy. The vibrations from the converter are intensified and coupled by the probe. The tip of the probe (sonotrode) immersed in the liquid vibrates longitudinally and transfers this movement as a pressure wave in the liquid, thereby creating alternative positive and negative pressure areas.

In order to vary the power of the system, we proceed by varying the ratio of transformation at the output transformer (autotransformer). This causes a variation of voltage across the piezoelectric transducer and thus the electric power equivalent to the transmission power of the ultrasonic waves.

METHODS

The developed control board has the role of shaping the electrical signal collected at the entrance of the galvanometer to make it usable. Most often, it is a question of giving the sampled signal a compatible level with the digital processing unit. A conditioner includes a filter for reducing interference present in the signal and a voltage amplifier (Boyé et al., 2006; Azan, 2006; Milsant 1993; Floyd, 1999; Klaasen, 1996).

Display of the digital ultrasonic power

The development of an application based on the PIC16F877 cannot be done without programming the microcontroller, the simulation and then the execution of the corresponding program (Rousset and Six, 2000; Wozniak, 2006). To do this, a program and a PIC16F877 programmer are needed.

In general, a microcontroller is only sensitive to the given instructions, encoded in hexadecimal. To validate the protocol for display and storage of power of our digital Ultrasonic generator, we used a code written in C language (Brian and Ritchie, 1978). Writing and transcription of the hex code is provided by the software Mikro C.

Dependence of the ultrasonic generator power

Figure 3 shows the functional block diagram of the feed back control system of the ultrasound generator power where V_C is the reference voltage, $\epsilon = V_C - V$, the voltage error or discrepancy, the control voltage V_R , Γ the engine torque and the feedback signal V through the user or a conventional feedback.

Figure 3: Block diagram of ultrasound generator (UG) control

To each value of the command voltage V_C correspond, at a steady flow rate, a rotational speed, power or torque of the operator and an error voltage ϵ .

The command entered using a keyboard give the power and duration of emission of our waves produced by our ultrasound generator. To collect or measure the power received by our suspension, power that can vary depending on the density of the suspension, we will have a regulator to make corrections of accuracy, stability and speed. A DC motor equipped with a speed reducer is coupled to the cursor of the autotransformer for adjusting the desired power. In other words, the effect of the feedback voltage V will be materialized as follows:

We set an engine torque Γ (operating point or equilibrium) through V_C . If the loads torque (medium viscosity) increases or decreases, the system will compensate. Note that the change in the composition of a suspension, constitutes for our control device, a disturbance due to the fact that the power received by the latter will not be the

same because of its density. This has as effect; an adjustment of the power delivered by our ultrasound generator such that the power received by the suspension is the same. With regards to the previous, the chart from the dependency of our Ultrasound generator is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Dependency Flow Diagram.

RESULTS

Calibration enables us to obtain information on the sensitivity of the galvanometer and the linearity of response (power) or not with respect to the variation of the amplitude of ultrasonic vibration. By varying the amplitude of the ultrasonic waves for a body of titanium $m = 1.5g$ in 200 ml of distilled water, we obtained the following values of power output of the ultrasound production device.

Table 1: Variation of the ultrasound generator power with respect to voltage

	Output power (%)	6	6.8	8	10	14	18	20	22	26	30	31	40	43
	Theoretical Power (W)	13.68	16.58	20.64	20.68	34	44	51	54.86	66.9	75.45	79.22	96	100.5
1 st trial	Voltage (mV)	5.2	6.2	7.6	9.2	12.2	15.6	18.1	19.4	23.5	26.5	27.8	33.6	37.2
	Output Power (W)	15	17	20	25	35	45	50	55	65	75	77.5	100	100.5
2 nd trial	Voltage (mV)	5.2	6.2	7.5	9.15	12.2	15.65	18.1	19.42	23.45	26.45	27.75	33.6	37.2
	Output Power (W)	15	17	21	25	36	45	52	56	66	75	77.5	100	101.5
Mean value	Mean Voltage (mV)	5.2 ±0.0 0	6.2 ±0.00	7.55 ±0.05	9.175 ±0.02 5	12.2 ±0.00	15.625 ±0.00	18.1 ±0.00	19.41 ±0.01	23.47 5 ±0.02 5	26.47 5 ±0.02 5	27.77 5 ±0.02 5	33.6 ±0.00	37.2 ±0.00
	Mean output power (W)	15 ±0.0 0	17 ±0.00	20.5 ±0.5	25 ±0.00	35.5 ±0.5	45 ±0.00	51 ±1.00	55.55 ±0.5	65.5 ±0.5	75 ±0.00	77.5 ±0.00	100 ±0.00	101.5 ±0.5

The experimental measurements allowed us to know that the law of variation of the power with respect to voltage is a straight line equation: $y = 2.9068x - 1.4026$, with a coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.9976$ where y is the power (W) and x the Voltage (mV). We integrated this equation in the program. The correlation coefficient being 0.9, it indicates a relatively strong relation between the variation of the voltage and power.

Figure 5: UG power graph with respect to voltage.

CONCLUSION

The objective of this work was to develop the digital control of the power of an ultrasonic generator. The power control of this device that we inserted in the process of mechanical mixing of liquid foods is very important. Indeed, from its control depends the quality, reproducibility of liquids to be manufactured.

The calibration of the analog display, the writing of a program corresponding to the calibration curve and the management process by the PIC16F877 device helped develop the power display and storage circuit thus computerized ultrasonic generator.

We have shown that the benefits of the new system compared to the old are: the high accuracy on the power setting (10th mW) and the conservation of the basic function of the ultrasound generator. Given the measurements made at different powers for homogenization of liquid food, we can establish a database to be used in any process. Finally, these data can be made in the networks to any remote accessibility.

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